

Magnetic inclination effects in star-planet magnetic interactions

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Abstract

A large fraction of the exoplanets discovered today are in a close-in orbit around their host star. This proximity allows them to be magnetically connected to their host, which lead to efficient energy and angular momentum exchanges between the star and the planet. We carry out three-dimensional magneto-hydrodynamic simulations of close-in star-planet systems to characterize the effect of the inclination of the planetary magnetic field on the star-planet magnetic interaction. We parametrize this effect in scaling laws depending on the star, planet, and stellar wind properties that can be applied to any exoplanetary systems around cool stars.

1 Introduction

More than 3000 exoplanets have been discovered and characterized so far thanks to multiple space missions (*e.g.* Kepler, Corot) and ground-based observations (*e.g.* HARPS, HIRES). The closest and largest planets are the easiest to detect, leading to a significantly biased first sample of exoplanets towards close-in hot Jupiters. Such planets have been observed around almost all solar-type stars, and recently even around TTauri stars (Donati *et al.*, 2016; Yu *et al.*, 2017), which questions today their formation and migration processes.

The proximity of such planets to their host opens new star-planet interaction possibilities compared to solar-system planets (see, *e.g.* Lanza, 2017). In particular, magnetic, tidal and radiative interactions are significantly amplified in such systems (Cuntz *et al.*, 2000), which could lead to observable traces in either transient phenomena such as stellar flares in UV, X or radio wavelengths (Zarka, 2017), or in the population of exoplanets itself (*e.g.* McQuillan *et al.*, 2013). In the past years, a significant effort has been pursued to improve our understanding of the physical processes behind these interactions in order to qualify and quantify their potential effects.

We will focus here on one of these interactions, namely the magnetic interaction between a cool star driving a solar-like wind and a planet sustaining its own magnetosphere. The close orbit of the planet leads to a sub-alfvénic interaction between the planet and the ambient wind, alike the interaction of jovian natural satellites with the magnetosphere of Jupiter (Kivelson *et al.*, 2004), which are known to lead to observable aurorae near the pole of Jupiter (Bonfond *et al.*, 2013). The magnetic interaction can lead to multiple effects, among which energy (in the form of Alfvén waves) and angular momentum (in the form of a magnetic torque) exchanges between the star and the planet (for a review, see Strugarek 2017). The energy channeling was quantified analytically by Saur *et al.* (2013), and both effects were further parametrized by Strugarek (2016) using three-dimensional numerical simulations. The intensity of magnetic star-planet interactions is known to strongly depend on the magnetic topology of the

interaction (Ip *et al.*, 2004; Strugarek *et al.*, 2014, 2015), *i.e.* on the relative inclination of the planetary magnetic field with respect to the ambient stellar wind magnetic field.

We extend in this proceeding the work of Strugarek (2016) to parametrize self-consistently the effect of magnetic topology. In previous works, the two extreme topologies ('aligned' vs 'anti-aligned') were characterized. We use additional numerical simulations to pave the parameter space continuously in between the two. We describe the new simulations in Section 2.1 and propose an updated parametrization of the magnetic torque and energy flux due star-planet magnetic interactions in Section 2.2. We conclude in Section 3 and lay out the future improvements of the underlying numerical model necessary to derive more realistic scaling laws.

2 Inclination effects in star-planet magnetic interaction

We base this work on the numerical exploration described in Strugarek (2016) using the PLUTO code (Mignone *et al.*, 2007). We model the magnetic interaction between a close-in planet and its host star in the magneto-hydrodynamics (MHD) formalism in 3D, by considering the star and the planet as boundary conditions. Here we extend the series of simulations by adding three new simulations where the inclination of the planetary magnetic field changes from anti-aligned to perpendicular to aligned with respect to the stellar wind magnetic field. We consider a orbital radius $R_{\text{orb}} = 6R_*$, thus these new cases are to be compared to case 7 in Strugarek (2016) (see Appendix). All the details of the numerical setup were given in Strugarek *et al.* (2015); Strugarek (2016), we do not reproduce them here and refer the interested reader to those works.

2.1 The effect of inclination

We define the angle between the ambient stellar wind magnetic field \mathbf{B}_w and the planetary magnetic field \mathbf{B}_P by Θ_M . The overall topology of the interaction in each case is show in Fig. 1. The leftmost and rightmost cases were already studied in Strugarek (2016) and correspond respectively to the

Figure 1: Topology of the magnetic interaction for the five cases studied. The topology changes from a closed magnetosphere (left, anti-aligned configuration) to an almost completely open magnetosphere (right, aligned configuration).

anti-aligned ($\Theta_M = 180^\circ$) and aligned ($\Theta_M = 0^\circ$) cases. The three additional cases in between correspond to successive inclinations of the planetary field by 45° , the central case corresponding to a perpendicular inclination ($\Theta_M = 90^\circ$). We observe immediately that the magnetosphere transits from a closed magnetosphere (left) to an almost open magnetosphere (right). The volume occupied by the closed planetary field lines decreases steadily when transiting from the anti-aligned to the aligned configuration.

Our goal here is to quantify the impact of this inclination on the global properties of the interaction, namely on the energy (in the form of a Poynting flux) and angular momentum (in the form of a magnetic torque) exchanges in between the orbiting planet and the central star. These two quantities have already been parametrized separately for the anti-aligned and aligned configurations in Strugarek (2016). We calculate the magnetic Torque \mathcal{T} by integrating the angular momentum balance on concentric spheres around the planet location. The net resulting torque defines the torque applying to the orbiting planet (see Strugarek *et al.*, 2015). The integrated Poynting flux \mathcal{P} is calculated by computing the integral of the Poynting flux through the Alfvén wings (see also Strugarek *et al.*, 2015). We report their variation as a function of the inclination angle Θ_M in Figure 2. The torque is normalized by the orbital angular momentum of the planet $J_p = M_P (GM_\star/R_{\text{orb}})^{1/2}$ (M_P and M_\star are the masses of the planet and the star). As expected, both the torque and the Poynting flux are maximized when the magnetic topology is aligned ($\Theta_M = 0^\circ$) and minimized when the interaction is anti-aligned ($\Theta_M = 180^\circ$).

In an analytical development of the magnetic star-planet interaction, Saur *et al.* (2013) suggested the Poynting flux channeled in the Alfvén wings would be proportional to $\cos(\Theta_M/2)$. In their study, the formalism they chose did not let them consider the case of purely anti-aligned case, which we include here. We first fitted the dependency we observe with a generic $a + b \cos(c\Theta_M)$ formulation. The fitted trend with our numerical results gives $c \sim 1$ for both the torque and the Poynting flux (orange lines in Figure 2). Due the low number of points used in this fit, one must be careful not over-interpret this fitting. If we exclude the anti-aligned case, and try to fit to a formula compatible with results from Saur *et al.* (2013) (*i.e.* $a + b \cos(\Theta_M/2)$), we find a good agreement for the Poynting flux only (green dashed lines in Figure 2). As a result, we suggest to use the $\cos(\Theta_M)$ (orange) fit for the magnetic torque, and either the $\cos(\Theta_M)$ (orange) or the

$\cos(\Theta_M/2)$ (green) fit for the Poynting flux. In the remainder of this work we will focus on the $\cos(\Theta_M)$ (orange) fit for both quantities.

2.2 Parametric formulations

The magnetic torque and Poynting fluxes have been parametrized in Strugarek (2016) through

$$\mathcal{T} = A_0 \pi (c_d P_t M_a^\beta \bar{\eta}_a^{\nu_1}) \cdot (R_P^2 R_o \bar{\eta}_P^{\nu_2}) \cdot (\Lambda_P^\alpha), \quad (1)$$

$$\mathcal{P} = A_1 \pi (c_d S_w M_a^\xi \bar{\eta}_a^{\nu_3}) \cdot (R_P^2 \bar{\eta}_P^{\nu_4}) \cdot (\Lambda_P^\chi), \quad (2)$$

where we c_d is the drag coefficient; P_t the total pressure in the stellar wind at the orbital position; M_a and S_w the alfvénic Mach number and Poynting flux of the stellar wind at the same location; Λ_P the pressure ratio between the magnetic pressure in the magnetosphere of the planet and the wind pressure P_t ; $\bar{\eta}_a$ the anomalous ohmic dissipation coefficient in strong current sheets in the stellar wind; and $\bar{\eta}_P$ the ohmic dissipation coefficient associated to the Pederson conductivity in the ionosphere of the planet (see Strugarek 2016 for more details).

The parameters $A_0, A_1, \beta, \nu_1, \nu_2, \alpha, \chi, \nu_3, \nu_4, \xi$ were fitted separately for aligned and anti-aligned cases. We aim here at including the topology of the interaction Θ_M directly into the formulation. We know from Strugarek (2016) that the exponents of M_a are the parameters the most sensitive to the topology. As a result, combining with the results from Section 2.1 we suggest the following parametrization:

$$\mathcal{T} = A_0 \pi f_{B_0}(\Theta_M) \left(c_d P_t M_a^{\beta_0 f_{\beta_1}(\Theta_M)} \bar{\eta}_a^{\nu_1} \right) \cdot (R_P^2 R_o \bar{\eta}_P^{\nu_2}) \cdot (\Lambda_P^\alpha), \quad (3)$$

$$\mathcal{P} = A_1 \pi f_{B_1}(\Theta_M) \left(c_d S_w M_a^{\xi_0 f_{\xi_1}(\Theta_M)} \bar{\eta}_a^{\nu_3} \right) \cdot (R_P^2 \bar{\eta}_P^{\nu_4}) \cdot (\Lambda_P^\chi), \quad (4)$$

where the exponents and multiplicative constants are now sought to be independent of Θ_M , and $f_x(\Theta) = 1 + (x - 1) \cos(\Theta)$. We consider now the full set of three-dimensional simulations from Strugarek (2016) to which we add the three inclined cases presented before to find the optimal parameters for the overall torque \mathcal{T} and Poynting flux \mathcal{P} . As in Strugarek (2016), we define the fitted quantities as

Figure 2: Magnetic torque (top) and Poynting flux (bottom) as a function of the magnetic inclination Θ_M (blue circles). Two fits of the simulation results are shown by the orange plain line ($\propto \cos(\Theta_M)$) and the green dashed line ($\propto \cos(\Theta_M/2)$).

$$A_{\text{eff}} = \frac{\mathcal{T}}{P_t R_{\text{orb}} c_d}, \quad (5)$$

$$\bar{\mathcal{P}} = \frac{\mathcal{P}}{c_d S_w}. \quad (6)$$

The resulting fits are shown in Figure 3 and the fitted parameters are reported in Table 1. Interestingly, the fitted exponents are fully compatible with the ones deduced in Strugarek (2016), and nicely generalize them to an inclination-dependant formulation.

It has to be noted that here, we have not fully characterized the dependancy of the scaling laws (3- 4) with respect to the ohmic dissipation properties of the stellar wind and ionospheric plasma (exponents ν_X), which would require a dedicated study with a more extensive set of inclined cases.

Keeping in mind this caveat, the parametrization (3- 4) can now be used in conjunction with stellar wind models (e.g. the simple 1D *starAML model*, see Réville *et al.* 2015) to estimate

Figure 3: Fitted results for the torque (top) and Poynting flux (bottom) for the full set of simulations, as a function of the pressure ratio Λ_P (see text). Each circle represents a simulation and is coloured by the magnetic inclination angle Θ_M .

orders of magnitude of the effects of magnetic star-planet interactions in observed systems.

3 Conclusions

In this proceeding we have extended the parameters study of Strugarek (2016) dedicated to the modelling of magnetic star-planet interactions in close-in systems. We have explored the effect of inclination of the planetary field with respect to the ambient stellar wind and characterized its impact on the energy and momentum exchanges triggered by the interaction. The results from our 3D modelling are found to be compatible with the analytical prediction of the Poynting flux in Alfvén wings proposed by Saur *et al.* (2013).

Previously, both effects have been parametrized independently for two extreme topological situations: the anti-aligned configuration, where the magnetosphere is closed, and the aligned configuration, where the polar magnetic field lines of the planet directly connect to the stellar wind magnetic field. Here we revisited this separate parametrization

Table 1: Fit parameters for the torque and Poynting flux

Parameter	Value
$A_0 [\pi R_P^2]$	7.38 ± 0.36
B_0	1.53 ± 0.01
β_0	-0.24 ± 0.02
β_1	1.13 ± 0.16
α	0.27 ± 0.01
$A_1 [\pi R_P^2]$	4.55 ± 0.62
B_1	1.81 ± 0.02
ξ_0	1.11 ± 0.07
ξ_1	-0.29 ± 0.06
χ	0.23 ± 0.02

to provide a continuous parametrization between these two topologies (see Equations 3-4). These parametrized formulae can be combined with simpler stellar wind models than the global 3D model used here to provide estimate of the energy fluxes and angular momentum exchanges in observed star-planet systems. An example of such an application can be found in Strugarek *et al.* (2017) where the magnetic migration due to the magnetic torque is systematically compared to the tidal migration of a close-in planet.

Finally, a number of improvements to our 3D star-planet interaction model need to be undertaken to provide even more realistic scaling laws. First, the effects of ohmic diffusion and inclination need to be studied together to improve the dependancy to $\bar{\eta}_a$ and $\bar{\eta}_P$ in Equations (3-4). Second, the boundary condition mimicking the planetary ionosphere is still a very crude approximation (see *e.g.* Strugarek *et al.* 2014). More realistic boundary conditions can be designed (Duling *et al.*, 2014), and ultimately a true magnetosphere-ionosphere boundary condition (*e.g.* Merkin & Lyon, 2010) needs to be considered to model properly the magnetospheric response. Third, we have considered here planet sustaining their own magnetospheres. Given the strong stellar wind pressure, it is likely that some of the close-in planets cannot sustain a proper magnetosphere. The magnetic coupling then depends on the internal properties of the planet, and could be studied with the model used in this work. Fourth, and this is the last point, we also have considered that the planetary orbit was circular and perpendicular to the rotation axis of the star, which is not necessarily justified *e.g.* in the context multi-planetary systems. Inclination and eccentricity of the orbit would likely change the scaling laws proposed here. A significant development effort is needed to take into account such aspects in our star-planet magnetic interaction model, which we hope to carry out in a future work.

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